

RESPONS SISWA SMK TERHADAP E-TRAINING PERSIAPAN SELEKSI MASUK PERGURUAN TINGGI BERBASIS ANDROID

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk menghasilkan aplikasi E-Training berbasis Android yang valid dan praktis untuk seleksi masuk perguruan tinggi. Penelitian menggunakan model pengembangan *four-D* dengan 4 tahapan, yaitu *define*, *design*, *develop*, dan *desiminate*. Alat pengumpul data menggunakan lembar validasi dan angket. Teknik analisis data melalui uji validitas produk dengan melibatkan pakar/ahli, yaitu ahli desain dan ahli materi, serta uji praktikalitas yang melibatkan 28 siswa SMK Negeri 2 Pariaman. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa aplikasi E-Training berbasis Android dinyatakan sangat valid berdasarkan aspek substansi materi, komunikasi visual, desain evaluasi, dan pemanfaatan *software*, serta respons siswa terhadap aplikasi menunjukkan hasil dengan kriteria sangat praktis ditinjau dari daya tarik, proses penggunaan, kemudahan penggunaan, dan alokasi waktu. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, maka dapat disimpulkan bahwa aplikasi E-Training dapat digunakan bagi siswa sebagai latihan untuk persiapan seleksi masuk perguruan tinggi.

Kata Kunci: Android; aplikasi E-Training; seleksi masuk perguruan tinggi.

Abstract

The research aimed to produce valid and practical Android-based E-Training for college entrance selection. This research used a four-D development model with 4 stages, namely define, design, develop, and desiminate. The data collection tool used validation sheets and questionnaires. The data analysis technique was through product validity testing involving experts, namely design experts and material experts, as well as practicality tests involving 28 students of SMK N 2 Pariaman. The results showed that Android-based E-Training was declared to be very valid based on aspects of material substance, visual communication, evaluation design, and software utilization, and student responses to the application showed results with very practical criteria in terms of attractiveness, process of use, ease of use, and time allocation. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that E-Training can be used for students as an exercise to prepare for college entrance selection.

Keywords: Android; E-Training application; college entrance selection.